

Preserving the Existence of Radio through the Utilisation of Instagram

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Abstract:- Humans are highly social beings. The recent appearance of various social networking sites, and their usage at an explosive rate, illustrates the strong and fundamental human desire for social belonging and interpersonal exchange. As the rate of conventional media consumption is gradually decreasing, traditional media companies are seeking for a chance of survival by using social media. This research analyses how radio as one of conventional media uses Instagram, as a social media platform which is a form of new media. By conducting in-depth interviews with four different informants and applying Miles and Huberman's qualitative data analysis technique which involved data reduction, data display, and conclusion drawing and verification, the results of the research found that the seven characteristics of New Media Theory by Denis McQuail are applicable for the utilisation of Instagram as a social media platform of 101.4 Trax FM Jakarta.

Keywords:- Instagram, Social Media, Radio, New Media.

I. INTRODUCTION

According to JakPat (2016) survey published by eMarketer, the age groups with the biggest Instagram usage in Indonesia are 16 – 19 year-olds and 20 – 25 year-olds with the total of 73.6% and 73.8% (of respondents) respectively. As a radio with a target audience aged between 15 and 25 years old, 101.4 Trax FM Jakarta use their Instagram as a way to communicate with their listeners on a digital platform.

As stated in the article "Social Media as a Communication Tool – Is It Really That Important?" (2010), social media is considered to be an effective communication tool in several ways. As a medium of

promotion, social media contributes through its immediacy, to a healthy and direct relation between brands and their public in an online environment. This immediacy offers the public the ability to be present, to communicate, to influence and retain a stronger position towards brands.

Other radios in Jakarta that share the same target audiences as Trax FM also use Instagram as a platform to interact with their listeners. Their top three competitors which are Prambors, Gen FM and Mustang post a variety of contents which are distinct to each radio stations.

Frequency (FM)	Radio	Number of Listeners
101.4	Trax FM	137.000
102.2	Prambors	803.000
98.7	Gen FM	1.375.000
88.0	Mustang	373.000

Table 1:- Radio Audience Measurement

Source: Nielsen (2017)

The data above is an official data published by Nielsen which was retrieved from the Department of Research and Development of MRA Broadcast Media Division. The data is the radio audience measurement of Trax FM, Prambors, Gen FM and Mustang from April – June 2017. Based on the data, 101.4 Trax FM Jakarta would be an intriguing subject of research because they have the smallest number of listeners compared to its competitors. Thus, their existence and popularity are in jeopardy in the Indonesian radio industry. In order for Trax FM to survive, innovation will be required in order for them to maintain their existence.

It may be concluded that Instagram could be the best platform to use for Trax FM Jakarta. Ganesha (2017) stated that Instagram claims it records more than 45 million active users every month in Indonesia and a user growth of more than 100 percent since last year, confirming the general suspicion that Indonesians are among the world's most active Instagram users. Indonesia is one of its most astonishing markets with an immense growth of users — from 22 million in early 2016 to 45 million as of July 2017.

As a radio with the lowest number of listeners compared to its competitors, Instagram is used as a social media platform by 101.4 Trax FM Jakarta to attract, gain and retain more listeners. It might be the best tool for the survival of 101.4 Trax FM Jakarta, considering the fact that the age of their target audience is between 15 – 25 years old and the exact same age group is actually the most active Instagram users.

Based upon the background it is identified that the problem of this research is: “How does 101.4 Trax FM Jakarta use Instagram as a tool to preserve their existence?”

II. NEW MEDIA

According to McQuail (2005, p. 136), new media is a distinct set of communication technologies that share certain features apart from being new, made possible by digitalisation and being widely available for personal use as communication devices. The key medium characteristics that are relevant to differentiate between new media and old media, seen from the perspective of an individual ‘user’ are:

- Interactivity: as indicated by the ratio of response or initiative on the part of the user to the ‘offer’ of the source/sender
- Social presence (or sociability): experienced by the user, meaning the sense of personal contact with others that can be engendered by using medium
- Media richness: the extent to which media can bridge different frames of reference, reduce ambiguity, provide more cues, involve more senses and be more personal
- Autonomy: the degree to which a user feels in control of content and use, independent of the source
- Playfulness: uses for entertainment and enjoyment, as against utility and instrumentality

- Privacy: associated with the use of medium and/or its typical or chosen content
- Personalisation: the degree to which content and uses are personalised and unique

III. MASS MEDIA

McQuail (2010, p.4) referred mass media to the organized means of communicating openly, at a distance, and to many in a short space of time. Turow (2010) stated mass media are the technological instruments through which mass communication takes place (e.g. newsprint, television, radio).

According to Turow (2010, p. 420) radiotelephony or radio, for short, is the broadcast of speech and music through wireless transmission. The term broadcasting refers to radio transmissions that can be widely received, a term that originally comes from an agricultural term meaning to scatter seed over a board area rather than in particular places. Its initial purpose was not for entertainment, but rather for communication purposes. McLeish (2005) stated that radio has expanded into an almost universal medium of communication.

➤ *Social Media*

David Scott (2015, p. 56) defined that social media provides the way people share ideas, content, thoughts, and relationship online. Social media is different from the so-called mainstream media because anyone can create, comment on, and add to social media content. Social media can take the form of text, audio, video, images, and communities.

IV. METHODS

This research will be conducted through qualitative descriptive studies. It tends to draw from naturalistic inquiry, which requires a commitment to studying something in its natural state to the extent that is possible within the context of the research area. Therefore, there is no manipulation of variables and no prior commitment to any one theoretical view of a target phenomenon (Lambert and Lambert, 2012).

The analysis of Instagram as a social media platform of 101.4 Trax FM Jakarta is a research that uses qualitative approach. Qualitative research has the objective of explaining the phenomenon deeply, through deep data collections. This research focuses more on the depth, or the quality, instead of the quantity of the data. (Kriyantono, 2009, p. 56).

The approach of this research is case study. Daymon and Holloway (2002) stated that a case study is an intensive examination, using multiple sources of evidence, of a single entity which is bounded by time and place. Usually it is associated with a location. The 'case' may be an organisation, a set of people such as a social or work group, a community, an event, a process, an issue or campaign.

V. INFORMANTS

Due to its subjective characteristics, the selection of informants is very important for any qualitative research. It is compulsory to collect information and evidence from a sample or a portion of the population, as it is very unlikely to collect data from everyone that is related to the topic. Qualitative research should be purposive sampling which allows the researcher to gain in-depth information through the certain criteria that has been determined for the purpose of the research (Daymon and Holloway, 2002). In this case, to collect all necessary information needed in order to understand how Trax FM Jakarta utilise their Instagram. The informants that are chosen have to be individuals that are credible in the fields of the research, which consists of internal informants and external informants.

VI. INTERACTIVITY

One of the characteristics of New Media is interactivity and Instagram is a platform with features that enable people to interact with one another by giving likes, sending comments and personal messages, and many more. In the social media field, that is also known as social media engagement. Social media engagement measures the public shares, likes and comments for an online business' social media efforts. Engagement has historically been a common metric for evaluating social media performance but doesn't necessarily translate to sales. (Big Commerce, n.d.)

Tomi mentioned the objective of why Trax FM made an Instagram account from his perspective as a senior producer and announcer "It's for awareness and interaction. The awareness is by creating content that would catch people's attention so people could see what Trax has created. Then what's the interactive part? Well, through the comments. We always write captions that would trigger people to comment, and that way they could post a comment. A two-way communication, by using captions in a form of a question. So, we could interact with them."

The digital department of MRA Broadcast Media Division prioritise engaging contents, the type of contents that are published with an objective to create social media engagement. In this case, they create contents that will trigger their followers to respond by giving likes, comments, and sharing the post. According to Tomi, the posts that receive the most engagements are contents that contain quizzes, especially quizzes that enable the followers and listeners to win prizes.

Jason Blake, a social media specialist, has confirmed that Trax FM Jakarta made the right decision to prioritise Instagram as the social media platform to interact with their listeners and followers. He stated "Overall, the target audience of social media is mostly people aged 13 – 35 years old. And people within that age range are very active on Instagram. So I think it's a very good strategy for Trax FM to build their brand, or their social media through Instagram. So I think it's a very good decision".

Social Presence (or Sociability)

Schluter (2014) stated that Social Presence, or in this case Social Media Presence, does not refer to whether one's social media accounts exist or does not exist, but rather how they post and engage on their social media accounts. In general, social media presence refers to how frequently one posts, the type of content that are posted, and the levels of engagement on one's social media accounts. Social media presence is not merely associated with how frequent one posts, but in order to have a good social media presence, the contents that are published should also be effective.

Some of the examples of having a good social media presence may include posting content daily that is relevant to the brand, posting with the type of communication and language that represents the brand, and sharing content that followers of the brand would understand and appreciate. In this subchapter, the researcher would discuss about how frequent Trax FM posts, the type of content that are posted, the levels of engagement on Trax FM’s Instagram account, and how effective they are.

One of the metrics for social presence is by analysing the levels of engagement on their account Social media engagement measures the public shares, likes and comments for an online business' social media efforts (Big Commerce, n.d.). According to Morrison (2015), engagement is the number of interactions people have with your content (e.g. likes, comments, shares, etc.).

INSTAGRAM OF 101.4 TRAX FM JAKARTA

Fig 1:- Number of Interactions, from Digital Department MRA BMD (2017)

Figure 1 is a more detailed data obtained from the digital department of MRA with precise numbers of followers, likes and comments received. The chart shows the progress of those three categories each month starting from October 2016 until April 2017. The researcher inquired Jason, a social media specialist, regarding the extreme gap between the number of interactions and the number of followers. He stated “If the followers do not find the content relevant and relatable enough, no matter how many followers they have, no matter how often they post on their Instagram account; it’s not going to perform well.” However, according to Michael, a follower of Trax FM’s Instagram, the contents that Trax FM publish through their Instagram account are beneficial for him. “As a follower and a listener, I’m able to gain new information because they are up-to-date.”

VII. MEDIA RICHNESS

According to McQuail (2005), media richness is the extent to which media can bridge different frames of reference, reduce ambiguity, provide more cues, involve more senses and be more personal. Littlejohn and Foss (2009, p. 641) stated that there are four factors that influence media richness. The researcher would also like to interpret and apply the four factors in adjustment to this research. Firstly, the ability of the medium to transmit multiple cues (e.g., vocal inflection, gestures). Secondly, immediacy of feedback (how rapidly the medium enables receivers to respond to messages). Thirdly, language variety (e.g., words, mathematics, art). Fourthly, the personal focus of the medium (the ability to personalize the message to the receiver).

As mentioned above, there are many features provided by Instagram that would enable the medium to transmit multiple cues. As mentioned by the digital content manager “We don’t only post regular photos, but we can also focus more on the audio and visual. That’s the advantage of using Instagram.” The researcher inquired about the most beneficial feature from Instagram according to the digital content manager and he mentioned that the digital department always try every new feature on Instagram. Then the department would observe which feature Trax FM’s followers like the most. Febry, the senior producer stated that the trends have also shifted; today followers are keener to check their Insta Story rather than the normal Instagram feed and followers would rather check on Insta Stories than scrolling downwards to check their feed.

As a social media specialist, Jason confirmed that Trax FM has optimised the features that are provided by Instagram. “Based on what I saw on their account, indeed they have optimised the features. They used the multiple images too.” Since 2017 Instagram provide a feature so users could post ten multiple images (including videos) in one content which looks like a slideshow. Trax FM Jakarta posts a range of pictures, videos, and multiple pictures hence creating a variety of content for their followers to see and enjoy so the followers would not get bored of a monotonous content. The type of language that are used on their photo captions are informal, due to the target audience of Trax FM Jakarta which are people between the age of 15 and 25 years old.

From the perspective of a follower, Michael could understand the captions of their Instagram posts easily because they are short, precise, and clear. “So even if you read it only once, you could understand it straight away. You wouldn’t have to read it over and over again.” He also mentioned that the poster designs that Trax FM publish are attractive enough because it shows a vivid yellow colour; the identity colour of 101.4 Trax FM Jakarta. The captions that are easy to understand are also the cause to why he would not comment on their posts, “Their captions only need to be read once and I understand it immediately, so I would only like their posts. I rarely post a comment.”

VIII. AUTONOMY

According to McQuail (2005), autonomy is the degree to which a user feels in control of content and use, independent of the source. The focus of research on this subchapter is whether the management of MRA Broadcast Media Division authorise the utilisation of Instagram, and if so, until what extent. The management of MRA Group does not fully control the digital department in terms of posting contents on the social media accounts. The extent of authorisation does not reach the point where the management micro-manage the content. However, in some cases the Head of Department in the MRA Broadcast Media Division Management requests content related to nationwide radio campaigns. Nevertheless, the occurrence of that is very rare.

From the Program Division’s point of view, Febry also mentioned that the management don’t have restrictions of the contents that are published. However usually they utilise every social media from each radio stations to promote some ongoing training programs from MRA Broadcasting Academy. According to Jason as a social media specialist, the method of promotion by MRA Group in this case is acceptable.

IX. PLAYFULNESS

According to McQuail (2005), playfulness is the use for entertainment and enjoyment, as against utility and instrumentality. The digital content manager stated that the types of posts with the most impressions besides quizzes are comical videos. He also mentioned that in year 2016 – 2017, the top trends on Instagram are video posts. Thus, it is also the reason why the digital department prioritise video contents; they focus on producing good videos to increase their reach and impressions.

The researcher inquired Jason, the social media specialist whether the Instagram content of Trax FM Jakarta was playful for their followers aged 15 – 25 years old, and he responded that the contents are not playful enough. He also stated that Trax FM should focus on being closer with their followers, try to find the insights of what content and hobbies they like. The contents that are

presented by Trax FM Jakarta are not relevant and relatable enough for their younger target audiences aged 15 years old. Even if the number of followers has reached around 20.000, he questions whether they are the right audience or not. “It seems like the contents are meant for people aged 25 years old and above.” He stated that the contents that are created by Trax FM might attract the wrong target audience, thus it becomes less engaging for the younger target audiences.

X. PRIVACY

Researcher has interpreted and adjusted the application of privacy to this research, which leads to the focus of research “How do they protect the privacy of their followers?” In MRA Broadcast Media Division, there are three departments who are able to obtain the data of their listeners and followers. The three departments are Program, Digital, Research and Development. The digital department shares the responsibility of handling and keeping the privacy of each listener’s and follower’s data. For quiz contents on Instagram, the privacy of the participants is well-kept because the digital department avoid making captions which triggers their followers to reveal their identities in public through comments.

XI. PERSONALISATION

McQuail (2005) stated that personalisation is the degree to which content and uses are personalised and unique. Trax FM’s Instagram posts should contain an element of the colour yellow in every picture if possible.

However, 102.2 Prambors FM Jakarta as the main competitor of 101.4 Trax FM Jakarta has the same tone colour, which is also yellow. As a social media specialist, Jason mentioned that one of the methods to differentiate the two radios are based on the content. “What type of content would they inject into the minds of their followers? A similar content could be discussed, but it will have to be tweaked so each radio would have a different angle regarding the same content.” He further explained, when people see the colour yellow, they would remember Prambors because the existence of Prambors has been longer than Trax FM which dates back to 1970s; meanwhile, Trax FM has just celebrated their 17th birthday. “So, if we

compare them based on the colour, there will be a large gap between Prambors and Trax FM, because people are more aware of Prambors.” He stated that in order for the public to differentiate the two brands, there must be a unique selling proposition for each radio.

XII. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the analysis, the methods of how Instagram is used as a social media platform of 101.4 Trax FM Jakarta could be analysed by using the seven characteristics of New Media by Denis McQuail, which are Interactivity, Social Presence, Media Richness, Autonomy, Playfulness, Privacy and Personalisation. Each character is present in this research and has been explained comprehensively in the previous chapter.

As a radio station, 101.4 Trax FM Jakarta prioritise their interactivity with the followers on Instagram in order to gain more listeners, and one of the methods is by posting engaging contents. Their social presences are indicated through the frequency of publishing contents, the type of contents that are published (organic and paid), the levels of engagement and effectiveness of their posts. Trax FM posts a minimum of four posts every day and are usually organic content, however the number of engagements are still very low compared to the number of impressions. This may lead to a conclusion that the contents that they publish are less effective because the contents are less relatable for the target audience.

The media richness on their Instagram account are shown through the utilisation of multiple Instagram features, the ability to convey a range of messages through photo captions and the content itself (pictures, videos, multiple pictures, Insta Story posts), the immediacy of feedback they receive through likes, comments, and direct messages, and lastly their ability to become personally close with their audiences. Trax FM are able to optimise every feature provided by Instagram which also allows them to receive and send immediate feedbacks, however the findings of engagement levels indicate that Trax FM Jakarta might not be personally close with most of their target audiences.

101.4 Trax FM Jakarta has the autonomy to post the

contents on their Instagram without a strict policy from the higher management of MRA Broadcast Media Division; however some event promotions made by MRA Group are mandatory for Trax FM to post on their Instagram. The playfulness of Trax FM Jakarta is mainly portrayed through the video posts, however most of the other contents are considered to be less playful for their younger target audience, hence resulting in the low number of engagements. The privacy of the listeners and followers are well kept by three departments, which are the Digital Department, Research and Development, and Program Division. As a brand, 101.4 Trax FM Jakarta has a specific personality and characteristic they would like to present on their Instagram account. One of them is through utilising the colour yellow in most of their posts as a form of brand identity. Unfortunately, Prambors as their main competitor also share the same brand colour which is yellow. This leaves Trax FM Jakarta in a difficult position to distinguish itself from the well-known competitor.

RECOMMENDATION

The researcher would like to suggest that the following research could use a quantitative method of text analysis between media content and target market. The research could analyse audience preferences in interacting with the media by conducting quantitative research using questionnaires as the data collection technique. Therefore, future research would be an analysis from a different perspective because it will draw on audience's point of view.

The results of this study can be used as an advice and suggestions for other radio stations that also utilise Instagram as the main social media platform to reach their target audience. The researcher would like to give a suggestion to Trax FM Jakarta to adjust the content of their Instagram account according to their target audience by posting contents which are suitable, relevant, and relatable for their age. Instagram could be the best platform to attract people between 15 – 25 years old and the Instagram of 101.4 Trax FM Jakarta is rich in media content, however it has not yet proven to suit the target audience and increase the number of engagements. It will be difficult for Trax FM Jakarta to survive if the followers and listeners cannot

relate to the contents posted on their Instagram account. Hence, the researcher would like to advise 101.4 Trax FM Jakarta to enhance the quality of their Instagram posts instead of the quantity.

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